

Solvent effect on alkaline fading of crystal violet in pure and aqueous mixtures of alcohols

J. Datta^{a*}, C. Bhattacharya^a, S. Sinha^b and K. K. Kundu^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, B. E. College (D.U.), P.O. Botanic Garden, Howrah-711 103, India

E-mail : jayatids@hotmail.com Fax : 91-33-26684564/2916

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Mahadevananda Mahavidyalaya, Monirampur, Barrackpore, 24-Parganas (N), India

^cPhysical Chemistry Section, Jadavpur University, Kolkata-700 032, India

Manuscript received 15 March 2004, revised 9 September 2004, accepted 23 September 2004

Chemical kinetics of alkaline fading of crystal violet has been studied in aqueous mixtures of methanol, ethanol, isopropanol and t-butanol by measuring the specific rate constant of the reactions spectrophotometrically in these solvent systems. The kinetic solvent effect has been analyzed in the light of Gibb's free energies of transfer of reactants and transition states from water to aqueous mixtures of alcohols, derived thereof. The observed variation of transfer free energy parameters, characteristic of the S_N2 reaction, with cosolvent compositions have been interpreted in terms of various specific and non-specific interactions of media with the reacting species and the transitions state involved in this reaction.

The triphenyl-methane dyes are known to be important analytical reagents for bacteriology. Micellar kinetics of alkaline fading of such dyes as well as the kinetic studies in relation to their pharmaceutical uses have been recently reported^{1,2}. Many of the earlier reports on chemical kinetics involving tertiary carbonium ion is based upon substituted nucleophilic bimolecular (S_N2) reactions using HO^-/RO^- as the standard nucleophile in different solvent systems³⁻⁵. Notably, in our earlier work kinetic behavior of similar process has been reported in poly-hydroxylic and some dipolar aprotic solvents⁴.

In the present work the kinetics of alkaline fading of crystal violet $[(4-Me_2N-C_6H_4)_3C^+Cl^-]$ has been reported in pure and aqueous mixtures of alcohols like methanol (MeOH), ethanol (EtOH), isopropanol (2-PrOH) and t-butanol (t-BuOH). Attempts have been made to evaluate the activation parameters dissected into individual contributions of initial and transition states, which lead to the understanding of the solvent effect on the kinetics of the chemical process. The specific rate constants (k_s) in respective solvents, derived thereof, help evaluate the transfer energies of initial state and transition state solvations, based upon the reaction $CV^+ + S^- \rightleftharpoons [TS]^\ddagger \equiv (CV^+S^-)^\ddagger$ where, CV^+ = reactant dye species, S^- = lyate ion (HO^- or RO^-) and TS = transition state. The ΔG_i^0 values of chloride^{6,7} and nucleophile HO^- or RO^- ⁸ were obtained earlier by the reference

electrolyte tetraphenylarsonium tetraphenylborate extra-thermodynamic assumption⁹.

Results and discussion

The kinetic solvent effect (KSE) values for the reaction $CV^+ + RO^- \rightleftharpoons [CV^+RO^-](TS) \rightarrow$ Product may be obtained as follows :

$$\delta(\Delta G)^\ddagger = \Delta G_i^0(TS) - [\Delta G_i^0(CV^+) + \Delta G_i^0(S^-)] \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Also } \delta(\Delta G)^\ddagger &= (\Delta G_s)^\ddagger - (\Delta G_w)^\ddagger \\ &= -RT \ln k_s + RT \ln k_w \\ &= -RT \ln (k_s/k_w) = \text{KSE} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{or, } -\text{KSE} &= -\delta(\Delta G)^\ddagger \\ &= \Delta G_i^0(TS) - \Delta G_i^0(CV^+) - \Delta G_i^0(S^-) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where, $\Delta G_i^0(X)$ stands for the free energy of transfer of the species X from water to aqueous mixture of alcoholic cosolvents and $(\Delta G_s)^\ddagger$ and $(\Delta G_w)^\ddagger$ stands for the free energy change of TS in aqueous cosolvent mixture and water respectively. In the present amphiprotic solvents (ROH), lyate ion is majorly the HO^- in water rich compositions while a substantial amount of conjugate ion RO^- is generated in solvent rich compositions. The free energy change of the lyate ion $\Delta G_i^0(S^-)$ is also a measure of the acidity of the mixed solvents relative to that of water according to the phenomenon

Table 1 represents the solubility data of CV⁺Cl⁻ salt at 25°C as well as the kinetic and thermodynamic parameters relative to the present reaction. With higher aliphatic alcohols, the solubility of CV⁺Cl⁻ is enhanced due to dispersion and soft-soft interaction of the solvent with the organic moiety of dye molecule¹⁰. The larger positive values of $\Delta G_{\text{t}}^{\text{d}}(\text{S}^-)$ with increasing wt% co-solvents as obtained from literature⁹ indicates increased destabilization of RO⁻ and reflects the acidity of the mixed solvents in the order : t-BuOH < 2-PrOH < EtOH < MeOH which conforms to what is expected from the positive inductive effect of the co-solvents.

In Fig. 1 the observed KSE ($RT \ln k_{\text{s}}/k_{\text{w}}$) – composition profile suggests that aqueous methanol behaves somewhat differently from its higher homologs. In case of the former the KSE value increases gradually till 20 wt% of co-solvent beyond which the value remains almost constant, whereas in aqueous mixture of EtOH, 2-PrOH and t-BuOH, the KSE value passes through a distinct minimum at 20 wt% for

each of the co-solvents and then increase gradually throughout the composition range mostly in the order EtOH > 2-PrOH > t-BuOH.

Fig. 1. Variation of KSE with different wt% of the co-solvents for the decolourisation of crystal violet at 25°C : (●) MeOH; (*) EtOH; (Δ) 2-PrOH; (□) t-BuOH.

Table 1. Variation of dielectric constant (ϵ), k_{s} (min^{-1}), $RT \ln k_{\text{s}}/k_{\text{w}}$ (kJ mol^{-1}), and the transfer free energies (kJ mol^{-1}) $\Delta G_{\text{t}}^{\text{d}}(\text{CV}^+\text{Cl}^-)$, $\Delta G_{\text{t}}^{\text{d}}(\text{Cl}^-)$, $\Delta G_{\text{t}}^{\text{d}}(\text{CV}^+)$, $\Delta G_{\text{t}}^{\text{d}}(\text{S}^-)$, $\Delta G_{\text{t}}^{\text{d}}(\text{TS})$, $\Delta G_{\text{t,cav}}^{\text{d}}(\text{CV}^+)$, $\Delta G_{\text{t,cav}}^{\text{d}}(\text{TS})$, $\Delta G_{\text{t,B}}^{\text{d}}(\text{CV}^+)$ and $\Delta G_{\text{t,i-d}}^{\text{d}}(\text{CV}^+)$ with alcohol-water mixtures at 25°C

Co-solvents	Wt% co-solvents	ϵ	$k_{\text{s}} \times 10^2$	$RT \ln k_{\text{s}}/k_{\text{w}}$	$\Delta G_{\text{t}}^{\text{d}}(\text{CV}^+\text{Cl}^-)$	$\Delta G_{\text{t}}^{\text{d}}(\text{Cl}^-)$	$\Delta G_{\text{t}}^{\text{d}}(\text{CV}^+)$	$\Delta G_{\text{t}}^{\text{d}}(\text{S}^-)$	$\Delta G_{\text{t}}^{\text{d}}(\text{TS})$	$\Delta G_{\text{t,cav}}^{\text{d}}(\text{CV}^+)$	$\Delta G_{\text{t,cav}}^{\text{d}}(\text{TS})$	$\Delta G_{\text{t,B}}^{\text{d}}(\text{CV}^+)$	$\Delta G_{\text{t,i-d}}^{\text{d}}(\text{CV}^+)$
MeOH	0	78.3	2.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	10	74.1	9.4	3.6	3.5	3.8	-0.3	-0.2	-4.1	-1.1	-2.1	0.2	0.2
	20	69.2	17.5	5.1	1.9	6.9	-5.0	-0.2	-10.3	-3.3	-6.0	0.4	0.4
	40	59.6	23.9	5.9	-1.6	16.2	-17.8	0.02	-23.7	-4.3	-7.8	0.8	1.0
	60	51.0	37.8	7.0	-3.6	24.8	-28.4	0.9	-36.3	-7.5	-13.6	1.4	1.6
	80	42.0	41.0	7.2	-4.8	32.7	-37.5	1.8	-42.9	-10.7	-19.5	2.3	2.5
EtOH	100	33.0	51.0	7.8	-	44.5	-	2.7	-	-13.7	-24.8	3.6	3.6
	10	72.8	2.5	0.3	0.6	4.0	-3.4	0.7	-3.0	-6.4	-11.8	0.2	0.2
	20	67.0	2.5	0.3	-0.6	7.4	-8.0	1.6	-6.7	-3.4	-6.2	0.4	0.4
	40	56.0	4.8	1.9	-2.8	17.5	-20.3	4.5	-17.7	-7.9	-14.5	1.1	0.9
	60	46.0	12.2	4.2	-4.2	27.0	-31.2	8.3	-27.1	-12.9	-23.5	1.9	1.6
	80	35.0	30.6	6.5	-5.1	36.0	-41.1	12.7	-34.9	-17.8	-32.5	3.3	2.6
2-PrOH	100	25.3	80.0	8.9	-	20.2	-	17.4	-	-22.6	-40.9	5.5	4.3
	10	71.4	1.4	-1.1	1.3	3.9	-2.6	1.8	0.3	-2.3	-5.5	0.3	0.2
	20	65.0	0.9	-2.2	-0.9	8.4	-9.3	3.5	-3.6	-15.3	-28.3	0.5	0.3
	40	53.0	2.9	0.7	-1.9	20.0	-21.9	7.0	-15.6	-12.1	-22.3	1.3	0.5
	60	41.0	7.5	3.0	-3.3	30.0	-33.3	10.6	-25.7	-18.7	-34.3	2.4	1.4
	80	29.0	28.8	6.4	-3.9	40.0	-43.9	13.9	-36.4	-25.8	-47.0	4.5	2.5
t-BuOH	100	20.2	-	-	-	-	-	17.8	-	-32.2	-58.2	7.6	4.6
	10	70.0	1.0	-2.0	-0.3	8.2	-8.5	1.4	-5.1	-2.8	-5.1	0.3	0.1
	20	61.3	0.8	-2.5	-1.8	14.8	-16.6	3.7	-10.4	-6.1	-11.3	0.7	0.3
	40	44.0	1.5	-0.9	-4.1	17.5	-21.6	8.0	-12.7	-12.7	-23.3	2.1	0.7
	60	31.0	5.2	2.1	-5.6	22.5	-28.1	10.6	-19.6	-20.3	-37.1	4.0	1.3
	80	20.0	42.5	7.3	-6.7	27.5	-34.2	12.0	-29.5	-27.8	-50.6	7.7	2.4
	90	16.2	163.6	10.7	-	-	-	12.5	-	-34.8	-62.7	13.9	4.8

Note

$$\Delta G_1^0(\text{CV}^+) = \Delta G_{1,\text{cav}}^0(\text{CV}^+) + \Delta G_{1,\text{Born}}^0(\text{CV}^+) + \Delta G_{1,\text{i-d}}^0(\text{CV}^+) + \Delta G_{1,\text{i-id}}^0(\text{CV}^+) + \Delta G_{1,\text{disp}}^0(\text{CV}^+) \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta G_1^0(\text{TS}) = \Delta G_{1,\text{cav}}^0(\text{TS}) + \Delta G_{1,\text{d-d}}^0(\text{TS}) + \Delta G_{1,\text{d-id}}^0(\text{TS}) + \Delta G_{1,\text{disp}}^0(\text{TS}) \quad (6)$$

where the terms ΔG_1^0 in the right hand side of eqs. (5) and (6) represent transfer free energy of the initial state for cavity, Born electrostatic, ion-dipole, ion induced-dipole and dispersion effects, and that of the transition state for cavity, dipole-dipole, dipole induced-dipole and dispersion effects, respectively^{12,13}. The ΔG_1^0 values for cavity formation, Born and ion-dipole interactions were computed with the help of relations used earlier^{12,13}. Notably, during such computation the diameter of IS and TS have been evaluated using the diameter of CV^+ as 6.73×10^{-8} cm, obtained from the molar volume of its chloride salt¹³. In each of the alcoholic solvent, the values of cavity interactions are found to be larger in magnitude for the ion pair formed in the TS than those for IS which is a single cationic species. It has larger contribution from Table 1 that $\Delta G_{1,\text{cav}}^0$ for both IS and TS have larger contribution than the Born electrostatic effect. This may be attributed to the low surface charge density of large sized dye-species. Although the ion-induced dipole and dipole-dipole contributions of initial state (IS) and TS could not be computed due to the non-availability of refractive index/polarizability data of the reactant dye, the dispersion interactions of the large dye species are expected to contribute significantly to the stabilization of both IS and TS as was observed in case of cavity formation. The observed minima in Fig. 1 for t-BuOH and 2-PrOH seemingly suggest that, as the order of acidity of the solvents decreases in case of 2-PrOH and t-BuOH, the amalgamated effects of Born, i-d and i-id interactions of CV^+ are likely to be much more than that of d-d and d-id effects of TS [CV^+S^-], conforming to what is expected from physico-chemical considerations like dielectric constant and inductive effect of solvents and co-solvents. In fact, the TS solvations are relatively high compared to those for IS in the alcoholic solvents which substantiate the higher reaction rates of the $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ type reaction in such solvent mixtures.

Experimental

The co-solvents (MeOH, EtOH, 2-PrOH) were purified by usual procedure for the preparation of 10–90 wt% aqueous mixtures of co-solvents⁹. Saturated solubility of the chloride salt of crystal violet (G.R., E. Merck) in different aquo-organic solvent mixtures was measured at 25°C using JASCO spectrophotometer. Decolorization of the dye was studied spectrophotometrically at 25°C taking $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 590$ nm². The reaction kinetics was assumed to be pseudo-first order by keeping the concentration of CV^+ and NaOH $1 \times$

Fig. 2. Variation of KSE with $\Delta G_1^0(\text{S}^-)$ in different wt% of the co-solvents for the decolourisation of crystal violet at 25°C: (●) (*)MeOH; EtOH; (Δ) 2-PrOH; (□) t-BuOH.

In water-rich mixtures of ROH, the three-dimensional bulk structure is more ordered than in pure water, and thus the initial fall in the reaction rate is majorly due to the contribution of OH^- ions available in relatively less concentration. After the composition of maximum structure promotion (~20 wt%) is attained, further addition of ROH initiate a rapid structural collapse releasing RO^- to react even faster than OH^- ¹¹. This is quite evident from the increasing trend of KSE in both the Figs. 1 and 2. However, in case of MeOH, small size CH_3^- group generally does not affect the structure-promoting behavior in water rich compositions and thus, instead of showing a minimum, the KSE values passes through a broad maximum due to availability of both the lyate ions OH^- and OR^- . It is apparent that progressive decrement of dielectric constant (ϵ) values¹² as shown in Table 1, of the co-solvents have hardly any influence on the present $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ reaction. Fig. 2 represents plots of KSE vs $\Delta G_1^0(\text{S}^-)$ values for different binary mixture compositions (ref. eq. (3)). It is found that except in aqueous MeOH, the KSE values increase with increasing positive values of $\Delta G_1^0(\text{S}^-)$ which reflects reduced acidity of these mixed solvents (ref. eq. (4)). It is important to note that the value of $\Delta G_1^0(\text{CV}^+) - \Delta G_1^0(\text{TS}) \neq 0$ (ref. eq. (2)) and also the slopes of these plots are far from unity. Evidently, KSE of the reaction in these aqueous alkanols is an overall representation of specific solute-solvent interactions associated with physico-chemical properties of reacting species in the medium.

The similarity in the variation of ΔG_1^0 values of initial and transition states with solvent composition are followed from Table 1. Now $\Delta G_1^0(\text{CV}^+)$ and $\Delta G_1^0(\text{TS})$ are likely to be guided by the following solvation terms^{12,13}.

$10^{-5} M$ and $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ respectively. In pure non-aqueous medium, alkoxides (Fluka) used were methoxide, ethoxide and t-butoxide. The isopropoxide was however not available. The kinetics in pure t-BuOH could not be studied due to the exceedingly high reaction rate in this solvent. However, the kinetics in 90% t-BuOH was performed.

References

1. A. K. Bajpai, J. Bajpai and S. Shukla, *J. Macromol. Sci., Pure & Appl. Chem.*, 2002, **39**, 489.
2. Y. Zhang, X. Li, J. Liu and X. Zeng, *J. Dispersion. Sc. & Tech.*, 2002, **23**, 473.
3. C. F. Wells, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1980, 1494.
4. U. Mandal, S. Sen, K. Das and K. K. Kundu, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1986, **64**, 300.
5. J. Datta, A. Bhattacharya and K. K. Kundu, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 115.
6. K. Bose, K. Das, A. K. Das and K. K. Kundu, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1978, **74**, 1051.
7. Y. Marcus, "Ion Solvation", John Wiley & Sons Ltd., New York, 1985.
8. J. Datta and K. K. Kundu, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1982, **86**, 4055 and relevant references therein.
9. S. Sinha, P. K. Guha and K. K. Kundu, *Z. Phys. Chemie. (NF)*, 1990, **167**, 221.
10. A. B. Naim, "Hydrophobic Interactions", Plenum Press, New York, 1980.
11. K. Das, A. K. Das, K. Bose and K. K. Kundu, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, **82**, 1242.
12. J. I. Kim, A. Cecal, H. J. Born and E. A. Gomaa, *Z. Phys. Chem. (NF)*, 1978, **110**, 209.
13. J. W. Weigl, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1956, **24**, 577.